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Development of Fuel Consumption Correction Factors for GTL Synthetic Diesel Fuel in Diesel Vehicles under Field Operating Conditions

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Abstract

This study develops and experimentally justifies speed-dependent fuel consumption correction factors for gas-to-liquid (GTL) synthetic diesel fuel used in existing diesel vehicles. The experimental basis of the research was field testing of an ISUZU NQR71PL diesel vehicle operated with conventional petroleum diesel fuel and GTL synthetic diesel fuel under comparable conditions. The main performance indicators included maximum vehicle speed, acceleration time up to 60 km/h, and steady-speed fuel consumption at 40, 50, 60, 70, 80 and 90 km/h. The results showed that the maximum speed of the vehicle remained practically unchanged when GTL fuel was used, whereas the acceleration time increased moderately from 15.91 s to 16.86 s. The volumetric fuel consumption of GTL fuel was higher than that of petroleum diesel by 4.56-6.10%, depending on the speed mode. This increase is mainly associated with the lower density of GTL fuel and the corresponding decrease in fuel mass delivered per unit volume. Based on the obtained results, speed-dependent correction factors for GTL fuel consumption were calculated and an average factor of 1.055 was proposed for preliminary operational accounting. The study confirms that GTL synthetic diesel fuel can be used in existing diesel vehicles without major structural modifications; however, separate fuel-consumption norms should be established for its practical implementation.

Keywords: *GTL fuel; synthetic diesel; fuel consumption norm; correction factor; ISUZU NQR71PL; field test; low-carbon fuel; diesel vehicle.*

1. Introduction

Diesel engines remain widely used in road transport, agricultural machinery, construction machinery and stationary power units because of their reliability, high torque characteristics and relatively high thermal efficiency. At the same time, the environmental limitations of petroleum diesel fuel, including emissions of nitrogen oxides, carbon monoxide, unburned hydrocarbons, particulate matter and greenhouse gases, require the introduction of cleaner fuel alternatives [1-4]. Gas-to-liquid

(GTL) synthetic diesel fuel is one of the practically relevant solutions for reducing the environmental burden of diesel operation while preserving existing diesel-engine infrastructure. GTL fuel is produced from natural gas through synthesis-gas generation and subsequent Fischer-Tropsch synthesis. Compared with conventional diesel fuel, GTL fuel typically has a higher cetane number, lower sulfur content, reduced aromatic hydrocarbons and a predominantly paraffinic composition [5-9]. However, the introduction of GTL fuel into real transport practice cannot be evaluated only through its chemical and environmental advantages. Vehicle fleets and transport enterprises usually account for fuel consumption in volumetric units, especially in liters per 100 km. Since GTL fuel has a lower density than petroleum diesel fuel, its volumetric consumption may be slightly higher even when vehicle traction and speed characteristics remain practically unchanged [6, 8, 14].

For this reason, a separate operational approach is needed for GTL fuel. If conventional diesel consumption norms are directly transferred to GTL fuel without correction, fuel accounting may become inaccurate. Therefore, it is necessary to develop correction factors that reflect the difference between petroleum diesel and GTL synthetic diesel fuel under real operating conditions. The aim of this study is to develop and justify fuel consumption correction factors for GTL synthetic diesel fuel based on field testing of an ISUZU NQR71PL diesel vehicle. The novelty of the study is the operational interpretation of GTL field-test results through fuel consumption correction factors intended for practical vehicle-fleet use.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Test vehicle and fuel types

The experimental research was carried out using an ISUZU NQR71PL diesel vehicle. This vehicle type is widely used in urban and regional freight transportation and represents a typical light-duty diesel platform for evaluating synthetic fuels under operational conditions. Two types of fuel were used in the comparative experiment: conventional petroleum diesel fuel and GTL synthetic diesel fuel. The same vehicle was used for both fuels, and the tests were conducted without major structural modification of the engine or fuel system. This made it possible to evaluate GTL fuel as a near-drop-in synthetic diesel fuel for existing diesel vehicles. The main physicochemical differences between petroleum diesel and GTL fuel are shown in Table 1. In vehicle operation, density, viscosity, cetane number, sulfur content and aromatic hydrocarbon content are especially important because they affect injection, ignition delay, combustion stability and exhaust-emission formation [5-9].

Table 1. Typical physicochemical differences between petroleum diesel and GTL synthetic diesel fuel.

Parameter	Unit	Petroleum diesel	GTL synthetic diesel
Cetane number	-	48-52	60-70
Density at 15 deg. C	kg/m ³	820-845	about 765-790
Kinematic viscosity at 40 deg. C	mm ² /s	2.5-3.5	1.7-2.4
Sulfur content	ppm	up to 10 or more depending on standard	<5
Aromatic hydrocarbons	%	present	very low

Fuel type	-	petroleum-derived mixture	paraffinic Fischer-Tropsch fuel
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Figure 1. Experimental documentation of GTL fuel testing

(a) PIUSI digital fuel-flow meter
the test vehicle

(b) Laboratory engine test stand

(c) GTL fuel samples for field tests (d) Refuelling process of

Figure 1. Combined photographs of the GTL field-testing process, including fuel metering equipment, laboratory test equipment, fuel samples, GTL storage barrels and refuelling of the ISUZU NQR71PL vehicle.

2.2. Experimental indicators

The comparative assessment was based on three groups of operational indicators: maximum vehicle speed, acceleration performance and steady-speed fuel consumption. Maximum speed characterizes the ability of the vehicle to maintain high-speed operation. Acceleration time to 60 km/h characterizes transient dynamic response. Steady-speed fuel consumption characterizes operational economy. Fuel consumption was measured at 40, 50, 60, 70, 80 and 90 km/h. These modes were selected because they cover the most typical operating range for a light-duty truck in urban, suburban and intercity conditions. For each mode, the vehicle was operated under comparable road, loading and environmental conditions.

2.3. Calculation procedure

The relative change in fuel consumption when switching from petroleum diesel to GTL fuel was calculated according to Eq. (1):

$$\Delta q = ((q_{\text{GTL}} - q_{\text{D}}) / q_{\text{D}}) \times 100\%, \quad (1)$$

where q_{GTL} is the fuel consumption during GTL operation, and q_{D} is the fuel consumption during petroleum diesel operation.

To adapt diesel fuel consumption norms for GTL operation, a GTL correction factor was introduced according to Eq. (2):

$$K_{\text{GTL}} = q_{\text{GTL}} / q_{\text{D}}, \quad (2)$$

where K_{GTL} is the fuel consumption correction factor. If K_{GTL} is greater than 1.0, the volumetric GTL fuel consumption norm must be increased relative to the petroleum diesel norm.

The estimated GTL fuel consumption norm can be expressed as Eq. (3):

$$q_{\text{GTL,norm}} = K_{\text{GTL}} \times q_{\text{D,norm}}. \quad (3)$$

The simplified energy supplied to the engine in one injection cycle can be expressed as Eq. (4):

$$Q_f = \rho_f \times V_f \times H_u, \quad (4)$$

where ρ_f is fuel density, V_f is injected volume and H_u is the lower heating value. This relation explains why a lower-density fuel can require higher volumetric consumption for comparable engine output [6, 8, 14].

3. Results

3.1. Vehicle performance indicators

The field-test results for maximum speed and acceleration time are presented in Table 2. The maximum speed of the vehicle operating on GTL fuel was close to the value obtained with petroleum diesel fuel. The acceleration time to 60 km/h increased moderately, which can be explained by the lower density of GTL fuel and the fact that the standard fuel system calibration was not specially optimized for GTL operation.

Indicator	Unit	Petroleum diesel	GTL synthetic diesel	Relative difference
Maximum speed	km/h	104.17	105.50	+1.28%
Acceleration time to 60 km/h	s	15.91	16.86	+5.97%

Table 2. Field-test performance results of the ISUZU NQR71PL vehicle.

3.2. Fuel consumption results

Fuel consumption results at different steady-speed modes are shown in Table 3. GTL fuel consumption was higher than petroleum diesel fuel consumption in all tested speed modes. The increase ranged from 4.56% to 6.10%.

Speed, km/h	Diesel, L/100 km	GTL, L/100 km	Absolute difference, L/100 km	Relative difference, %
40	15.42	16.36	0.94	6.1
50	15.06	15.95	0.89	5.91
60	13.84	14.55	0.71	5.13
70	14.04	14.68	0.64	4.56
80	14.42	15.22	0.8	5.55
90	14.62	15.46	0.84	5.75

Table 3. Fuel consumption of the ISUZU NQR71PL vehicle at different steady-speed modes.

Figure 2. Comparative diagram of petroleum diesel and GTL synthetic diesel fuel consumption at different vehicle speeds.

Figure 3. Relative increase in volumetric GTL fuel consumption compared with petroleum diesel fuel.

3.3. GTL correction factors

Based on the measured fuel consumption data, speed-dependent GTL correction factors were calculated. The results are presented in Table 4.

Speed, km/h	Diesel, L/100 km	GTL, L/100 km	Correction factor K_{GTL}	Increase, %
40	15.42	16.36	1.061	6.10
50	15.06	15.95	1.059	5.91
60	13.84	14.55	1.051	5.13
70	14.04	14.68	1.046	4.56
80	14.42	15.22	1.055	5.55

90	14.62	15.46	1.057	5.75
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Table 4. Calculated GTL fuel consumption correction factors.

Figure 4. Speed-dependent GTL fuel consumption correction factor and average recommended value.

The calculated correction factor varied from 1.046 to 1.061. For general operational accounting, an average correction factor of $K_{GTL,avg} = 1.055$ may be recommended for the tested vehicle under comparable field conditions.

For example, if the diesel norm for a vehicle is 15.0 L/100 km, the estimated GTL norm can be calculated as follows: $q_{GTL,norm} = 1.055 \times 15.0 = 15.83$ L/100 km.

4. Discussion

The obtained results show that GTL synthetic diesel fuel can provide performance characteristics close to those of petroleum diesel fuel in an existing diesel vehicle. The maximum speed remained practically unchanged, while the acceleration time increased only moderately. This confirms that GTL fuel can be used without major structural changes in the vehicle. The main operational difference was observed in volumetric fuel consumption. Since GTL fuel has lower density than petroleum diesel, the same injection volume contains a lower fuel mass. Although GTL may have a relatively favorable lower heating value per unit mass, its energy content per liter is lower. Therefore, in practical fuel accounting, GTL consumption expressed in liters per 100 km becomes higher [6, 8, 14]. From the practical point of view, this increase should not be interpreted only as a disadvantage. GTL fuel has important environmental and operational advantages: high cetane number, low sulfur content, reduced aromatic hydrocarbons and improved combustion stability. These properties can reduce smoke formation and particulate emissions and can improve the durability of exhaust after-treatment systems [5, 7, 9, 20, 21]. The proposed correction factor approach is important for transport enterprises because fuel accounting systems usually operate with fixed norms. If the petroleum diesel norm is used for GTL fuel without correction, actual fuel consumption may be incorrectly interpreted as excessive. The correction factor allows operators to adjust norms in a technically justified way. For Uzbekistan, where GTL production has strategic importance, the results can support practical recommendations for the introduction of synthetic diesel fuel into vehicle fleets

and stationary diesel units. However, further research should include direct exhaust-emission measurement, long-term fuel-system durability assessment and optimization of injection-control parameters.

5. Practical recommendations

1. When GTL synthetic diesel fuel is used in existing diesel vehicles, separate fuel consumption norms should be developed instead of directly applying petroleum diesel norms.
2. For preliminary operational calculations, an average correction factor of 1.055 can be used for the ISUZU NQR71PL vehicle under comparable field conditions.
3. For more accurate fuel accounting, speed-dependent correction factors should be applied: 1.061 at 40 km/h, 1.059 at 50 km/h, 1.051 at 60 km/h, 1.046 at 70 km/h, 1.055 at 80 km/h and 1.057 at 90 km/h.
4. GTL implementation should be accompanied by fuel-quality monitoring, technical inspection of fuel-system elements and, where possible, correction of fuel-injection parameters.
5. Environmental assessment should be continued using direct measurement of NO_x, CO, HC, PM and smoke opacity under real operating conditions.

6. Conclusions

1. The field tests confirmed that GTL synthetic diesel fuel can be used in an existing ISUZU NQR71PL diesel vehicle without major structural modification.
2. The maximum speed of the vehicle remained practically unchanged when GTL fuel was used, changing from 104.17 km/h for petroleum diesel to 105.50 km/h for GTL fuel.
3. The acceleration time to 60 km/h increased from 15.91 s to 16.86 s, which corresponds to an increase of approximately 5.97%.
4. GTL volumetric fuel consumption exceeded petroleum diesel consumption in all tested steady-speed modes. The increase ranged from 4.56% to 6.10%.
5. The calculated GTL fuel consumption correction factors ranged from 1.046 to 1.061. The average correction factor was 1.055.
6. The proposed correction factor can be used for the development of GTL fuel consumption norms for transport fleets operating existing diesel vehicles.
7. Further research should include emission measurements, long-term durability assessment and optimization of injection-control parameters for GTL operation.

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